

1-D Strain Live Script

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Axial Strain

Applying tension: like a spring the bar elongates until the elastic force counter balances the pulling:

The bar has an unloaded length L , a cross-sectional area A , it experiences a compressive or tensile force F and a squashing or elongation ΔL . The stiffness of the bar is given by Young's modulus E .

- The force per unit area is **stress**: $\sigma = \frac{F}{A}$
- The ratio of change in length over original length is **strain**: $\epsilon = \frac{\Delta L}{L}$
- Hooke's Law relates stress and strain through **stiffness**: $\sigma = E\epsilon$

External Force is proportional to total axial deformation $F \propto \Delta L$. In one-dimension, stress and strain are scalars. The force/stress and deformation/strain can be positive or negative corresponding to tension/stretching and compression/squashing respectively. The proportionality constant $K = \frac{AE}{L}$ is known as **the spring constant** or simply the stiffness of the bar:

$$F = -\frac{AE}{L} \Delta L$$

The Total Elastic Energy U stored in the bar is equal the work done moving an end through the deformation distance:

$$\int_0^W dW = \int_0^{\Delta L} F(\Delta L) d\Delta L \quad \therefore U = -\frac{AE}{2L} \Delta L^2$$

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The Internal Axial Force is constant throughout the bar this is independent of material changes. Each element of the bar transmits the axial force to its neighbouring elements on either side and the static equilibrium applies to the element:

$$\sum_{\text{horizontal}} F = 0 \quad \therefore F(x) + F(x + \delta x) = 0$$

$$\therefore F(x) = -F(x + \delta x)$$

The **Total Axial Deformation** (Displacement) ramps up through the bar. The total distortion $u|_0^x$ across the interval $[0, x]$ is given below. Deformation is offset relative to a chosen datum point - here we chose that all deformation occurs on the right i.e. $u(0) = 0$:

$$\int_0^{u(x)} du = \frac{F}{AE} \int_0^x dx \quad \therefore u|_0^x = \frac{F}{AE} x$$

This is distinct from the Deformed Axial Position of point on the bar x' which is the sum of the original position x and the total deformation between the datum point:

$$x'(x) = x + \frac{F}{AE} x$$

Local Formulation of Field Equations

Here we consider varying material stiffness $E(x)$ and varying cross-sectional Area $A(x)$.

- Internal force is constant throughout the bar.
- stress varies through the bar $\sigma(x) = \frac{F}{A(x)}$
- stiffness vary over the bar: $E(x) = \frac{d\sigma}{d\epsilon}$
- strain is the gradient of the axial displacement: $\epsilon = \frac{du}{dx}$

If we want to study the fields through the bar; strain field; energy density field etc...

1. Assume Continuum Hypothesis: treat the bar as a continuum. (for breakdown see continuum fallacy limit)
2. Zoom in to an infinitesimally small element where macroscopic scale variations become zero
3. Formulate local equations describing the field in terms of intensive variables - extensive variables must be switch it intensive (density/derivative) equivalents
4. Zoom out carry the local field equations back to the macroscopic level where variations are appreciable and field equations are applicable using parameters which are positional functions of intensive variables

At an infinitesimal scale the local stiffness is constant and variation in cross-sectional area across the 1-D element is zero. The strain of the element δu is still comparable to the length of the element δx :

We can work out the energy stored in an element using extensive variables at the infinitesimal scale:

$$\int_0^{\delta U} dW = \int_0^{\delta u} F(u) du$$

$$\delta U = \frac{AE}{\delta x} \int_0^{\delta u} u du = \frac{AE\delta u^2}{2\delta x}$$

$$\frac{dU}{dx} = \frac{AE\delta u^2}{2\delta x^2}$$

Next we can substitute extensive variables with intensive ones to form an equation that works at the macroscopic scale:

$$\frac{dU}{dx} = \frac{AE\delta u^2}{2\delta x^2} = \frac{AE\epsilon^2}{2} = \frac{1}{2}A\sigma\epsilon$$

Energy per unit length,

$$\left. \frac{dU}{dx} \right|_x \equiv \frac{1}{2}A(x)\sigma(x)\epsilon(x)$$

Energy density,

$$\left. \frac{dU}{dV} \right|_x \equiv \frac{1}{2}\sigma(x)\epsilon(x)$$

Back at the macroscopic scale we can use these field equations to calculate total energy in the bar:

$$U = \int_0^L \frac{dU}{dx} dx = \int_0^L \frac{1}{2}A(x)\sigma(x)\epsilon(x) dx$$

...or the energy in a section of the bar:

$$U|_{x_a}^{x_b} = \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \frac{1}{2}A(x)\sigma(x)\epsilon(x) dx$$

We can work out the stiffness of an element using extensive variables at the infinitesimal scale:

$$\delta K = \frac{AE}{\delta x} \quad \therefore \quad \frac{dK}{dx} = AE$$

Stiffness per unit length,

$$\left. \frac{dK}{dx} \right|_x = A(x)E(x)$$

Stiffness per unit volume,

$$\left. \frac{dK}{dV} \right|_x = E(x)$$

Back at the macroscopic scale we can use these field equations to calculate total stiffness of the bar:

$$K = \int_0^L \frac{dK}{dx} dx = \int_0^L A(x)E(x) dx$$

or the stiffness of a section of the bar:

$$K|_{x_a}^{x_b} = \int_{x_a}^{x_b} A(x)E(x) dx$$

Discrete Forces (Numerical Analysis)

Consider the case of a bar with fixed ends with single force applied to the centre of the beam, red components are anchored to the surroundings, an discrete axial force is applied at the centre of yellow bar causing stretching to the left of the midpoint and compression to the right of the midpoint as shown below. The force through the bar is no longer constant - there is a jump at the midpoint. Unfortunately, discrete forces introduce discontinuities to the fields acting inside the bar which become non-integrable over the singularity, we have split the problem into a set analytical problems over the sections in which there are no forces and in which fields vary smooth and continuously. Alternatively can treat the problem numerically using poor man's finite element analysis as presented

here.

Setup: For simplicity we'll, just a constant area and constant stiffness bar (we can play with these values in the Matlab live editor if desired):

```
N=31; % no. discretised position samples
x0=0.; x1=1.; % start & end position of bar
x=linspace(0,1,N); % discretised position

A = 10.*ones(size(x)); % A(x) cross-sectional area through the bar [m^2]
E = ones(size(x)); % E(x) stiffness through the bar [Nm^-2]

offset = 0.5*(x1-x0)/32; % offset for numerical gradient approximations
```

The **External Forces** act on the bar at discrete points: the applied force in the middle as well as reactive forces at the fixed ends:

```
F_applied=10.; % external force applied to bar [N]

F_external = zeros(size(x));
F_external(1) = - F_applied/2; % Apply external reactive force at 1
F_external(ceil(length(x)/2)) = F_applied; % Apply external reactive force at 1
F_external(length(x)) = - F_applied/2; % Apply external reactive force at 1

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
```

Warning: MATLAB has disabled some advanced graphics rendering features by switching to software OpenGL. For more information, [click here](#).

```
stem(x,F_external)
title('discrete applied force at centre and discrete reaction forces at ends')
ylabel('External Force [N]');
```


The **Internal Force** through the bar is just the *negative* cumulative sum of external forces along the bar. This is continuous on each side of the bar with a discontinuity at the midpoint:

```
F=-cumsum(F_external);           % calculate internal force [N]

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x,F)
title('continuous force through bar with discontinuities due to external forces')
ylabel('Internal Force [N]');
```


The corresponding **Stress** is looks as follows:

```
stress=F./A;

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x,stress)
title('positive stress (stretching) left & negative stress (squashing) right')
ylabel('stress []');
```


The corresponding **Strain** is the Axial Distortion per unit length i.e. the gradient of the distortion. The sign of strain through the bar corresponds to stretching on the left and squashing on the right:

$$\epsilon(x) = \frac{du}{dx} \quad \therefore \quad \epsilon(x) = \frac{F(x)}{A(x)E(x)}$$

```
strain=F./(A.*E);

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x,strain)
title('positive strain (stretching) left & negative strain (squashing) right')
ylabel('strain []');
```


Let's approximate the **Total Displacement** $u|_0^x$. We see distortion starts at zero on the clamped left end and increasing, then distortion decrease on the right until the distortion is zero again at the clamped right end. The middle of the bar gets distorted the most.

$$u(x)|_0^x = \int_0^x \frac{du}{dx} dx \quad \therefore \quad u(x)|_0^x = \int_0^x \epsilon(x) dx$$

```
u=cumtrapz(x, strain);

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x+offset,u);
axis([0,1,0,u(floor(N/2))*1.1]);
ylabel('axial displacement [m]');
```


The **deformation** is extreme given the silly numbers ive used. The midpoint has been pulled way over to the right:

$$x' = x + u(x)|_0^x$$

```
x_prime=u+x;

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x_prime,ones(size(x_prime)),'Marker','none');
ylabel('Bar');
axis([0,1,0,1]);
```


Working backwards we can always approximate the strain numerically from total distortion numerically:

```
strain2=[0,diff(u)];           % re-calculate the strain

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x,strain2);
ylabel('strain approximation []');
```


The elastic **Energy** per unit length shows the energy is distributed evenly through the bar - it accumulates as we aggregate it from left to right.

$$\left. \frac{dU}{dx} \right|_x \equiv \frac{1}{2} A(x) \sigma(x) \epsilon(x) \quad \therefore U \Big|_{x_a}^{x_b} = \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \frac{1}{2} A(x) \sigma(x) \epsilon(x) dx$$

```
U_prime=0.5.*A.*stress.*strain; % integrand
U=cumtrapz(x, U_prime);

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x,U)
ylabel('Cummulative Energy [J]');
```


It's also useful to visualise properties over the deformed position x' rather than the original. Here we see that the energy is more concentrated in the squashed side of the bar than the stretched side:

```
figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x_prime,U);
title('Energy Stored over the deformed bar (left to right)')
ylabel('Cummulative Energy [J]');
```


The **Stiffness** per unit length shows stiffness accumulates as we aggregate it from left to right. Stiffness is an Extensive property.

$$\left. \frac{dK}{dx} \right|_x = A(x)E(x) \quad \therefore K \Big|_0^x = \int_0^x A(x)E(x)dx$$

```
K_prime=0.5.*A.*E; % integrand
K=cumtrapz(x, K_prime);
```

```
figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x,K)
ylabel('Stiffness from left');
```



```
clear;
```

Distributed Loads

Often external forces are not applied at specific points but as forces per unit length $f(x) = \frac{dF(x)}{dx}$. This arrangement applies a distributed axial load over the bar. Assuming the worm drive is very stiff the load is applied evenly over the bar i.e. the force per unit length is constant. We could imagine other scenarios where the worm gear is more elastic or varies in stiffness - the motor applies torsion down the bar which is transmitted more efficiently at the end with the motor. With a bit of imagination we could imagine a wide variety of external force distribution along the bar.

Since force varies continuously (and provided $E(x)$ and $A(x)$ do also) we can understand the whole system analytically. Previously the internal force was extensive and we described the system using the first order differential equation:

$$F(x) = A(x)E(x) \frac{du}{dx}$$

Now the internal force is intensive $F|_a^b$ and system is described by a second order differential equation:

$$\frac{dF}{dx} = \frac{d}{dx} \left[A(x)E(x) \frac{du}{dx} \right]$$

Still we get corresponding discrete reaction forces generated at the fixed ends of the beam. At the infinitesimal scale the internal force is constant as studied previously. All our field equations we derived down there still apply so long as they don't contain the constant F term - they don't since we used the always intensive σ instead.

Setup: the beam is the same as before:

```
N=31; % no. discretised position samples
x0=0.; x1=1.; % start & end position of bar
x=linspace(0,1,N); % discretised position

A = 10.*ones(size(x)); % A(x) cross-sectional area through the bar [m^2]
E = ones(size(x)); % E(x) stiffness through the bar [Nm^-2]

offset = 0.5*(x1-x0)/32; % offset for numerical gradient approximations
```

The **External Force** is distributed over the bar (descretised mesh) as well we have the discrete reactive forces at each of the fixed ends:

```
F_applied=10.; % external force applied to bar [N/m]

F_external = F_applied./N.*ones(size(x));
F_external(1) = - F_applied/2; % Apply external reactive force at
F_external(length(x)) = - F_applied/2; % Apply external reactive force at

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x,F_external)
ylabel('External Force [N]');
```


The **Internal Force** $F(x)$ through the bar is just the negative cumulative sum of external forces along the bar. This is continuous through the bar and (maybe a wee bit) interestingly the internal force drops to zero at the midpoint of the bar - we could slice the bar here and the system would stay in static equilibrium,

```
F=-cumsum(F_external); % calculate internal force [N]

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x,F)
```

```
title('continuous force through bar with discontinuities due to external forces')
ylabel('Internal Force [N]');
```


The corresponding **Stress** is looks as follows:

```
stress=F./A;

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x, stress)
title('deminishing positive stress (stretching) left & increasing negative stress (squashing) right')
ylabel('stress []');
```


... **Strain** ishas the same profile:

$$\epsilon(x) = \frac{du}{dx} \quad \therefore \quad \epsilon(x) = \frac{F(x)}{A(x)E(x)}$$

```
strain=F./(A.*E);

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x, strain)
title('positive strain (stretching) left & negative strain (squashing) right')
ylabel('strain []');
```


The **Total Displacement** $u|_0^x$. We see distortion starts at zero on the clamped left end and increasing to the midpoint before decreasing to zero again at the clamped right end. The profile is now quadratic:

$$u(x)|_0^x = \int_0^x \frac{du}{dx} dx \quad \therefore \quad u(x)|_0^x = \int_0^x \epsilon(x) dx$$

$$\therefore \quad u(x)|_0^x = \frac{1}{AX} \int_0^x \frac{dF}{dx} x dx \quad \therefore \quad \frac{1}{AX} \left[\frac{1}{2} \frac{dF}{dx} x^2 + c \right]_0^x$$

```
u=cumtrapz(x, strain);

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x-offset,u);
axis([0,1,0,u(floor(N/2))*1.1]);
ylabel('axial displacement [m]');
```


The **deformation** gradually changes over the material: $x' = x + u(x)|_0^x$

```
x_prime=u+x;

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x_prime,ones(size(x_prime)), 'Marker', 'none');
ylabel('Bar');
axis([0,1,0,1]);
```


The elastic **Energy** per unit length shows the energy is distributed a little bit unevenly through the bar as we total from left to right.

$$\left. \frac{dU}{dx} \right|_x \equiv \frac{1}{2} A(x) \sigma(x) \epsilon(x) \quad \therefore \quad U \Big|_{x_a}^{x_b} = \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \frac{1}{2} A(x) \sigma(x) \epsilon(x) dx$$

```
U_prime=0.5.*A.*stress.*strain; % integrand
U=cumtrapz(x, U_prime);

figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x,U)
ylabel('Cummulative Energy [J]');
```



```
figure('Position', [100, 100, 800, 200]);
stem(x_prime,U);
title('Energy Stored over the defored bar (left to right)')
ylabel('Cummulative Energy [J]');
axis([0,1,0,0.4]);
```


The **Stiffness** per unit length hasn't changed.

```
clear ;
```